

HSBC's Role in Expanding CCP Totalitarian

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AN ACCESSORY TO CCP

HSBC **froze assets** of former HK lawmaker Ted Hui and his family **overnight**, without any court order or relation to Hui's legal charges, seemingly as **political retaliation** for him going into exile.

Banks in HK are **at the CCP's disposal to impose financial sanctions** on activists, silencing opposition.

**BANKING WITH HSBC =
BANKING AT THE MERCY OF THE TYRANNY**

Source: The Guardian

IFC 國際文宣組

(Picture source: Twitter: @lowsalarygirl: Bye HSBC¹)

HSBC Holdings plc (HSBC) published its annual financial statements as of 31 December 2020 as a part of FORM 20-F (HSBC annual report), filed with the Securities and Exchange Commission in Washington, D.C. 20549 as annual report pursuant to Section 13 or 15(d) of the Securities Exchange Act of 1934, on 24 February 2021².

Blocking PCAOB inspection gave rise to reliability problem of HSBC financial reporting

Both the financial statements and its internal control over financial reporting were given an unmodified audit opinion by PricewaterhouseCoopers LLP in London (PWC UK). But as informed by the website of US Public Company Accounting Oversight Board (PCAOB), positions taken by Chinese Communist party (CCP) authorities impede PCAOB's ability to oversee PCAOB-registered audit firms in mainland China and Hong Kong, from which there is an auditor (PWC HK) that performs referred work, including playing a substantial role, in the audits of HSBC as specified in the figure below. The audit work PWC HK performs is relied upon by the public company's principal auditor PWC UK. That work can be significant to the audit of the financial statements HSBC files with the SEC and should also be within the scope of PCAOB inspections.

“The position taken by authorities in mainland China may in some circumstances cause a registered firm located in another jurisdiction to attempt to resist PCAOB inspection of public company audit work that the firm has performed relating to the company's operations in mainland China. Only in mainland China and Hong Kong, however, is the position of the Chinese authorities effectively an obstacle to inspection of all, or nearly all, registered firms in the jurisdiction”.³

2019 HSBC Holdings plc CIK (0001089113)

Firm Name: PricewaterhouseCoopers LLP

Firm Country: United Kingdom

Filing Date: March 24, 2020

Participation of Other Accounting Firms:

- PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO CHARTERED ACCOUNTANTS LLP (1385) – India – 5% to less than 10%
- PricewaterhouseCoopers, S.C. (1128) – Mexico – 5% to less than 10%
- PricewaterhouseCoopers LLP (238) – United States – 10% to less than 20%
- PricewaterhouseCoopers (1389) – Hong Kong – 10% to less than 20%

(Picture source: PCAOB⁴)

Following National Security Law enforcement and all the branches of jurisdiction falling in the hands of CCP in Hong Kong, the overall operation environment of PWC HK and preparing and presenting financial statement in conformance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) deteriorated. Preparation and presentation of financial statements as well as audit work require exercising objective evaluation work professional judgement and scepticism that CCP disallows. UK Financial Reporting Council published a podcast to “discuss why challenge of management and a challenge culture is critical to high quality audit” on 2 March 2020.⁵ But what CCP needs is obeying orders of its central core leader i.e, General Secretary from Beijing.

Reliability problem of Internal Control and Relevant Impact

Therefore, it shouldn't be taken for granted that the HSBC financial statements and audit opinion delivered by PWC UK which should have been supported with sufficient and appropriate audit evidence aren't questionable. It should neither be taken for granted that the HSBC's internal control on financial reporting is based on criteria established in Internal Control - Integrated Framework (2013) issued by the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO) and auditor's report on its internal control over financial reporting is also supported with sufficient and appropriate audit evidence. If internal control of a bank is questionable, then it may have pervasive effects on the operation and financial reporting of HSBC, including taking deposits, granting loans, non-compliance with anti-money laundering requirements, giving and taking bribes, worker rights abuses, outsourcing and accounting fraud. Accounting fraud played an important role of covering up all the other problems caused by significant internal control deficiencies.

Financial reporting is an important element of corporate governance, besides risk management and internal control, according to the provisions of the UK Corporate Governance Code issued by the UK Financial Reporting Council. ⁶Given non-inspectable audit work papers by PCAOB and overall environment in Hong Kong of strong vulnerability to accounting fraud, it should never be taken for granted that the statement on compliance with UK Corporate Governance Code on page 308 of HSBC annual report made wasn't false and misleading.

Questionable loans to customers

The same payment transaction could be accounted for either as expenses, capitalised as assets or settlement of liabilities and reporting of such transaction is subject to management subjective judgement. If no strong internal control concerning financial reporting and payment including granting loans and advances to customers, payment to a company which is actually controlled by a relative of politically exposed persons (PEP) or directly to personal accounts actually controlled by PEP but without the name of PEP, would be debited to loans and advances to customers to cover up bribery, especially likely in terms of deals with CCP. Such loans and advances to customers would finally be derecognized or written off preceded by charging ECL allowances year on year.

It was shown on the consolidated balance sheet that loans and advances to customers carried at 1,037.987 billion US dollars as at 31 December 2020 ⁷as the largest item of assets by deducting allowance for expected credit loss (ECL) and other credit provisions 14 billion US dollars from gross carrying amount 1,052.477 billion US dollars (allowance rate at 1.38%: $14.49/1,052.477 \times 100\%$), which was indicated on page 165, accounted for 34.78% ($1,037.987/2,984.164 \times 100\%$) of total assets.

According to "Analysis of reported results by geographical regions" on page 108, Those granted in Asia accounted for largest portion on average for 45.58% (Calculation: $473.165/1,037.987 \times 100\%$).

	Europe	Asia	MENA	North America	Latin America	Intra-HSBC	Total
Footnotes	\$m	\$m	\$m	\$m	\$m	\$m	\$m
Net interest income	5,685	14,318	1,465	2,836	1,960	1,304	27,578
Net fee income	3,499	5,418	695	1,795	467	—	11,874
Net income from financial instruments held for trading or managed on a fair value basis	3,266	4,273	402	997	593	51	9,582
Net income from assets and liabilities of insurance businesses, including related derivatives, measured at fair value through profit and loss	327	1,699	—	—	55	—	2,081
Changes in fair value of other financial instruments mandatorily measured at fair value through profit or loss	1,747	17	3	2	40	(1,354)	455
Other income/(expense)	3,885	1,197	63	745	(95)	(6,936)	(1,141)
Net operating income before change in expected credit losses and other credit impairment charges	18,419	26,922	2,628	6,375	3,020	(6,935)	50,429
Change in expected credit losses and other credit impairment charges	(3,751)	(2,284)	(758)	(900)	(1,124)	—	(8,817)
Net operating income	14,668	24,638	1,870	5,475	1,896	(6,935)	41,612
Total operating expenses excluding impairment of goodwill and other intangible assets	(17,860)	(13,584)	(1,521)	(5,081)	(1,933)	6,935	(33,044)
Impairment of goodwill and other intangible assets	(1,014)	(78)	(65)	(226)	(5)	—	(1,388)
Operating profit/(loss)	(4,206)	10,976	284	168	(42)	—	7,180
Share of profit/(loss) in associates and joint ventures	1	1,856	(265)	—	5	—	1,597
Profit/(loss) before tax	(4,205)	12,832	19	168	(37)	—	8,777
	%	%	%	%	%		%
Share of HSBC's profit before tax	(47.9)	146.2	0.2	1.9	(0.4)		100.0
Cost efficiency ratio	102.5	50.7	60.4	83.2	64.2		68.3
Balance sheet data	\$m	\$m	\$m	\$m	\$m	\$m	\$m
Loans and advances to customers (net)	408,495	473,165	28,700	107,969	19,658	—	1,037,987

(Picture source: [SEC](#))

Wholesale analysis of credit risk on page 175 indicated that after adding other debt instruments, such as those at fair value through other comprehensive income, off-balance sheet financial instruments, to loans and advances to customers at amortised cost, those granted in Mainland China (PRC) for 118.163 billion dollars and in Hong Kong (HK) for 452.983 billion dollars accounted for 7.75% and 29.72% respectively.

Wholesale analysis

IFRS 9 ECL sensitivity to future economic conditions

ECL of loans and advances to customers at 31 December 2020 ¹	Gross carrying amount ²
	\$m
UK	430,555
US	201,263
Hong Kong	452,983
Mainland China	118,163
Canada	85,720
Mexico	25,920
UAE	44,777
France	164,899

(Picture source: [SEC](#))

On page 95 as shown on the graph below, the maturity analysis also informed that most loans were issued in Asia.

At 31 December 2020, the geographical analysis of loan maturity and interest sensitivity by loan type on a contractual repayment basis was as follows.

	Europe \$m	Asia \$m	MENA \$m	North America \$m	Latin America \$m	Total \$m
Maturity of 1 year or less						
Loans and advances to banks	10,185	48,885	8,565	3,277	3,053	73,965
Corporate and commercial	90,637	141,848	13,867	22,296	5,473	274,121
Non-bank financial institutions	14,292	19,664	288	5,390	250	39,884
	115,114	210,397	22,720	30,963	8,776	387,970
Maturity after 1 year but within 5 years						
Loans and advances to banks	3,221	3,093	1,060	27	20	7,421
Corporate and commercial	60,030	102,902	8,359	27,932	5,308	204,531
Non-bank financial institutions	6,668	9,620	91	3,464	811	20,654
	69,919	115,615	9,510	31,423	6,139	232,606
Interest rate sensitivity of loans and advances to banks and commercial loans to customers						
Fixed interest rate	44,953	4,404	4,802	5,261	1,345	60,765
Variable interest rate	24,966	111,211	4,708	26,162	4,794	171,841
	69,919	115,615	9,510	31,423	6,139	232,606
Maturity after 5 years						
Loans and advances to banks	136	135	—	—	—	271
Corporate and commercial	28,435	13,191	2,388	3,160	1,251	48,435
Non-bank financial institutions	1,213	2,354	—	438	36	4,041

(Picture source: [SEC](#))

But on page 86, it told us that the loans and advances granted in HK\$ only 222.138 billion US dollars, indicating that the remaining loans and advances to customers in HK have been granted in other currencies such as US dollars. It was partly verified by 2019 IMF HK report in the following graph.

Loans and advances, deposits by currency

\$m	At 31 Dec 2020						Total
	USD	GBP	HKD	EUR	CNY	Others ¹	
Loans and advances to banks	17,959	3,495	7,155	4,601	6,063	42,343	81,616
Loans and advances to customers	173,117	280,803	222,138	89,851	37,671	234,407	1,037,987

(Picture source: [SEC](#))

Fund Raised by Mainland Firms in Hong Kong SAR

(Billions of USD)

Note: 2019 refer to January to October figures.

Sources: HKEx, and WIND.

Contribution to Mainland-related Lending by Type of Borrower

(Percentage points, year on year)

Sources: CEIC, and IMF staff calculations.

Then which customers have been granted loans and advances in HK in US\$ rather than in HK\$? CCP has many entities in HK, some of which are listed on the HK Exchange.

HSBC's Loans to Huawei

Huawei and The China General Nuclear Power Group (CGN) are both military entities designated by US Department of Defense.

Qualifying Entities Prepared in Response to Section 1237 of the National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 1999 (PUBLIC LAW 105-261)

Aviation Industry Corporation of China (AVIC)	CLEARED
China Aerospace Science and Technology Corporation (CASC)	For Open Publication
China Aerospace Science and Industry Corporation (CASIC)	Jun 12, 2020
China Electronics Technology Group Corporation (CETC)	Department of Defense OFFICE OF PREPUBLICATION AND SECURITY REVIEW
China South Industries Group Corporation (CSGC)	
China Shipbuilding Industry Corporation (CSIC)	
China State Shipbuilding Corporation (CSSC)	
China North Industries Group Corporation (Norinco Group)	
Hangzhou Hikvision Digital Technology Co., Ltd. (Hikvision)	
Huawei	
Inspur Group	
Aero Engine Corporation of China	
China Railway Construction Corporation (CRCC)	
CRRC Corp.	
Panda Electronics Group	
Dawning Information Industry Co (Sugon)	
China Mobile Communications Group	
China General Nuclear Power Corp.	
China National Nuclear Corp.	
China Telecommunications Corp.	

20-S-1496

(Picture source: National Pulse⁸)

As reported by Yahoo on 11 January 2020 and first appeared on South China Morning Post, HSBC had taken part in billions of dollars of loans to Huawei because Meng Wanzhou allegedly had deceived the bank about its activities in Iran in that the Huawei Meng’s misrepresentations put HSBC’s economic interests at risk by preventing the bank from accurately assessing the risks of maintaining a business relationship with Huawei and based on Huawei Meng’s assurances, HSBC had negotiated a US\$900 million credit facility for Huawei in 2014, and took part in a syndicate that loaned US\$1.5 billion to Huawei in 2015. It was mentioned that, “HSBC had already been hit with US\$1.7 billion in forfeitures and penalties in 2012 as a result of its violation of US sanctions on Iran, Cuba, Libya, Sudan and Myanmar”.⁹

According to a statement of U.S. Department of Justice,

“in 2012 Huawei began a concerted effort to steal information about a robot that T-Mobile used to test mobile phones. In an effort to build their own robot, Huawei’s engineers allegedly violated confidentiality and non-disclosure agreements with T-Mobile by secretly taking photos of the robot, measuring it, and even stealing a piece of it... As early as 2007, Huawei employees allegedly began to misrepresent the company’s relationship with its Iranian affiliate, which is called Skycom. Huawei employees allegedly told banking partners that Huawei had sold its ownership interest in Skycom—but these claims were false. In reality, Huawei sold Skycom to itself. By claiming that Skycom was a separate company—and not an affiliate which Huawei controlled—Huawei allegedly asserted that all of its Iran business was in compliance with

American sanctions. These alleged false claims led banks to do business with the company and, therefore, to unknowingly violate our laws.”¹⁰

Huawei, engaged in genocide in Xinjiang, uses AI tech that can identify Uighur individuals, as reported by CNBC on 14 January 2021¹¹, and is a part of CCP’s Military-Civil Fusion Strategy, as told by the US Department of State on 12 March 2020.¹²

HSBC failed to analyse the substance of the transaction “Huawei sold Skycom to itself” in this respect, due to inherent restrictions of internal control, neglect or intentional collusion with CCP. If HSBC couldn’t analyse such transaction’s substance correctly, then it couldn’t be expected that HSBC could present its own financial statement fairly provided that substance over form principle must be followed for financial statements to be fair.

The failure of identifying the substance was not likely caused by judgement error. It was reported by ANS on 16 June 2020 that Pompeo said CCP had reportedly threatened to punish HSBC and to break commitments to build nuclear power plants in UK unless UK allowed Huawei to build its 5G network and Shenzhen-based Huawei is an extension of the CCP’s surveillance state. Another article of Gnews depicted the ownership problem of Huawei.¹³ Non sense! If HSBC feared to be punished by CCP on this ground, then it may also pay bribe in the name of granting loans and accounting for as such and there may be completely false accounting entries processed to prepare its financial statements based on this same ground. Because of HSBC’s such obscure representation, it’s reasonable to doubt that there may be loans or debts investment outstanding for bribery purpose.

HSBC sided with another PLA entity CGN

CGN partnered with EDF Energy on U.K. nuclear construction projects at the Hinkley Point and Sizewell sites and they were proposing to build a reactor at the Bradwell nuclear site in Essex. The latter company has been imposed a fine of €5 million (about \$5.9 million) on Électricité de France for providing false information about the Hinkley Point C new-build nuclear project in the United Kingdom by The Enforcement Committee of the Autorité des Marchés Financiers.¹⁴ HSBC advocated for CGN financing with the name of promoting green bond of CGN Wind Power.¹⁵ It was reported on 23 November 2015 by Reuters that 1Malaysia Development Bhd sold power assets to CGN for \$2.3 bn, in which deal HSBC advised for CGN.¹⁶

HSBC financed property price bubbles

According to gross loans and advances by industry sector over five years on page 138 of HSBC annual report, its loans are focused on real estate industry both for customers’ “first lien residential mortgages” and for suppliers of homes (i.e., real estate developers), increasing year on year.

	In accordance with IFRS 9			In accordance with IAS 39	
	2020 \$m	2019 \$m	2018 \$m	2017 \$m	2016 \$m
Personal	460,809	434,271	394,337	376,481	339,798
- first lien residential mortgages	352,282	322,178	293,333	278,173	249,778
- other personal	108,527	112,093	101,004	98,308	90,020
Corporate and commercial	527,088	540,499	534,577	522,248	465,827
- agriculture, forestry and fishing	7,445	6,898	6,701	6,302	5,261
- mining and quarrying	11,947	14,435	14,172	10,911	15,781
- manufacturing	93,906	104,380	105,704	115,531	112,965
- electricity, gas, steam and air-conditioning supply	16,200	15,040	16,044	17,397	14,302
- water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation	3,174	3,501	3,523	2,806	2,380
- construction	14,600	15,287	15,254	15,443	14,876
- wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	90,663	94,681	97,665	98,079	82,848
- transportation and storage	29,433	25,580	25,541	24,258	23,081
- accommodation and food	26,071	24,656	21,547	16,971	12,823
- publishing, audiovisual and broadcasting	19,979	19,971	21,172	18,405	19,058
- real estate	127,027	130,752	123,233	114,349	98,639
- professional, scientific and technical activities	24,072	24,122	22,573	18,094	15,557
- administrative and support services	26,423	25,714	25,103	19,960	15,707
- public administration and defence, compulsory social security	2,008	2,377	1,463	221	137
- education	2,122	1,900	1,829	1,490	1,033
- health and care	5,510	4,465	4,308	5,688	4,971
- arts, entertainment and recreation	3,437	2,824	5,041	3,003	2,490
- other services	13,110	14,276	13,913	20,354	16,989
- activities of households	802	791	830	—	—

(Picture source: [SEC](#))

Part of the loans for first lien residential mortgages flew to CCP regimes both in PRC and HK. Accompanied with more and more control enforced by CCP over HK, stamp duties levied on real estate have been increasing in the name of controlling prices to finance suppression on HK pro-democracy movement.

With effect from 20 November 2010, any residential property acquired on or after 20 November 2010, either by an individual or a company (regardless of where it is incorporated), and resold within 24 months (the property was acquired on or after 20 November 2010 and before 27 October 2012) or 36 months (the property was acquired on or after 27 October 2012), will be subject to a Special Stamp Duty (SSD). SSD is calculated by reference to the stated consideration or the market value of the property (whichever is the higher), at the following rates for different holding periods of the property by the seller or transferor before disposal –

Holding Period	The property was acquired on or after 20 November 2010 and before 27 October 2012	The property was acquired on or after 27 October 2012
6 months or less	15%	20%
More than 6 months but for 12 months or less	10%	15%
More than 12 months but for 24 months or less	5%	10%
More than 24 months but for 36 months or less	-	10%

With effect from 27 October 2012, unless specifically exempted, Buyer's Stamp Duty (BSD) is payable on an agreement for sale or a conveyance on sale executed for the acquisition of any residential property. BSD is charged at 15% on the stated consideration or the market value of the property (whichever is the higher).

(Picture source: [https://www.gov.hk/en/residents/taxes/docs/IRSD123\(E\).pdf](https://www.gov.hk/en/residents/taxes/docs/IRSD123(E).pdf))

No doubt that the taxes included in PRC residential property loan principals are not less than that levied in HK, some of which are included in the loan principals of real estate developers, such as

land deed tax levied on acquiring land use right from CCP regime. The following graphs illustrate what taxes at what rate have been levied on PRC properties to finance the CCP tyranny.

Value-added tax (VAT)

The sales or importation of goods, the provision of services and the sales of intangible properties and immovable properties are subject to VAT. For general VAT taxpayers, input VAT can be credited against output VAT.

The applicable VAT rate for general VAT taxpayers from 1 April 2019 are set out in the following table, and the rate for small-scale VAT taxpayers is 3%.

Industries	Applicable Tax Rate%
Sales or importation of goods	13
Sales or importation of necessity goods (such as agricultural products, water and gas, etc.) (Note)	9
Provision of repairs, replacement and processing services	13
Tangible movable property leasing services	13
Transportation services, postal services, basic telecommunications services, construction services, immovable property leasing services, sales of immovable properties, transfer of land use right	9
Value-added telecommunications services, financial services, modern services (except for leasing service), consumer services, sales of intangible properties (except for land use right)	6
Exportation of goods; Exportation of repair, replacement and processing services; International transportation service and spacecraft transportation services;	0

For taxpayers which are eligible for the above zero rate, generally they may be entitled to a credit or refund of the input VAT incurred. The VAT refund rate for exported services is the same as the applicable VAT tax rate. For exported goods, the VAT refund rates range from 0% to 13%. There is a prescribed formula for determining the amount of refund, under which full refund of input VAT are not available to many exported goods and the exporter will suffer different degree of export VAT costs.

In addition, a few types of qualified exported services may be applicable to the VAT exemption treatment. In that respect, the relevant input VAT incurred cannot be credited or refunded.

From 1 April 2019 to 31 December 2021, taxpayers of manufacturing and living service industries can enjoy an extra 10% VAT input credit based on its VAT input for the current period.

Since 1 April 2019, China introduced the pilot VAT refund policy. Taxpayers who fulfil certain requirements can apply for a refund of the input VAT credit balance.

Consumption tax

Consumption tax is levied on manufacturers and importers of specified categories of consumer goods, including tobacco, alcoholic beverages, high-end cosmetics, jewellery, fireworks, gasoline and diesel and certain petroleum products, motorcycles, automobiles, golf equipment, yacht, luxury watch, disposable chopsticks, wooden floorboard, battery and coating. The tax liability is computed based on the sales amount and/or the sales volume depending on the goods concerned.

Land appreciation tax (LAT)

LAT is levied on certain gains realised from real property transactions at progressive rates from 30% to 60%, based on the "land value appreciation amount" which is the consideration received from the transfer or disposition of real property less the "total deductible amount".

For taxpayers engaged in a real estate development business, the "total deductible amount" includes:

- The amount spent on obtaining the land use right;
- Costs of real property development and construction;
- Finance expenses, such as interest, may be deducted in certain circumstances. Other real property development expense (i.e. selling and administrative) are limited to 5% of the total amount expended to acquire the land use right and the costs of real property development and construction;
- Taxes in connection with the transfer of real property (generally stamp tax); and
- Additional deduction equal to 20% of the sum of the amount spent on obtaining the land use right and costs of real property development and construction is allowed.

For disposal of used properties, the deductible amount includes the assessed value of the used building and the taxes incurred upon the disposal.

Customs duties

The Customs shall levy import and export customs duty on goods that are allowed to be imported into or exported based on relevant Customs regulation. Customs are authorised to collect VAT and consumption taxes at the time of importation.

The Consignee of imported goods, consignor of export goods, and owner of entry articles are parties held liable for paying customs duties.

Import duties are categorised as normal tariff rate, Most Favoured Nation (MFN) tariff rate, contractual tariff rate, preferential tariff rate, tariff-rate quota (TRQ) rate, and temporary tariff rate.

The Country of Origin of imported goods also plays a part in determining the applicability of a number of other trade policies such as: TRQ, preferential tariffs, anti-dumping duty, anti-subsidy duty, etc.

Duty Reduction or Exemption: import and export goods are reduced with or exempted from customs duties, import VAT and consumption tax according to state regulations. There are statutory, specific and temporary duty reduction or exemption.

The importation of raw materials under Processing Trade is bonded, and Customs duty, import VAT and consumption tax exemption is allowed on the part to be re-exported after processing.

For goods that enter into and exit from the Customs special supervision zone, import duties and import VAT and consumption tax are held over at the time of importation, which are to be exempted for exportation, or to be paid for sales from Customs special supervision zone to domestic markets.

Stamp tax

All enterprises and individuals who execute or receive "specified documentation" are subject to stamp tax. Rates vary between 0.005% on loan contracts to 0.1% for property leasing and property insurance contracts.

Real estate tax

Real estate tax is a tax imposed on the owners, users or custodians of houses and buildings. The tax rate is 1.2% of the original value of buildings. A tax reduction of 10% to 30% is commonly offered by local governments. Alternatively, tax may be assessed at 12% of the rental value.

Motor vehicle acquisition tax

Motor vehicle acquisition tax is a tax at a rate of 10% of the taxable consideration. It will be levied on any purchase, import, self-production, receipt as a gift or award, etc. of an automobile, a tramcar, a trailer, or a motorcycle with a gas displacement of over 150 milliliters within the PRC.

Deed tax

Deed tax, generally at rates from 3% to 5%, may be levied on the purchase or sale, gift or exchange of ownership of land use rights or real properties. The transferee/assignee is the taxpayer.

Vehicle and vessel tax

Vehicle and vessel tax is a tax that is levied on all vehicles and vessels within the PRC. A fixed amount is levied on a yearly basis. Transport vehicles are generally taxed on a fixed amount according to own weight, with passenger cars, buses and motorcycles being taxed on a fixed unit amount. Vessels are taxed on a fixed amount according to deadweight tonnage.

Vessel tonnage tax

Vessel tonnage tax is levied on any vessel entering into a port inside the territory of the PRC from overseas and is collected by the customs authorities. The tax rates are categorised into preferential rates and ordinary rates depending on the nationality of the vessels. The tax payable is computed based on the net tonnage multiplied by the applicable tax rate that is determined depending on the net tonnage and the term of tonnage tax license.

Urban and township land-use tax

Urban and township land-use tax is levied on taxpayers who utilize land within the area of city, country, township and mining districts. It is computed on an annual basis, based on the space of area actually occupied by a taxpayer multiplied by a fixed amount per square meter that is determined by the local governments.

Arable land occupation tax

Arable land occupation tax is levied on companies and individuals who build buildings, structures or engage in non-agricultural development on arable land within PRC. It is computed based on the space of area actually occupied by a taxpayer multiplied by a fixed amount per square that is determined by the local governments and is settled in a lump sum.

Environmental protection tax

Resource tax

The exploitation of natural resources including crude oil, natural gas, coal, salt, raw metallic metals and non-metallic metals, etc. is subject to resource tax on a sales turnover or tonnage / volume basis. The range of tax rates are specified by the State Council. Resource tax is collected on the usage of water in 10 provinces and cities on a trial basis.

Tobacco tax

Tobacco tax is levied on taxpayers who purchase tobacco leaves within the territory of the PRC. The tax is assessed at the rate of 20% on the purchasing value and shall be settled with the tax bureau at the place of the purchase.

Cultural business development levy

Companies and individuals engaged in entertainment and advertising businesses shall pay cultural business development levy at 3% on the relevant income.

(Picture source: PWC¹⁷)

The principals of loans granted to customers finally go to developers as consideration for homes except those taxes paid to CCP regimes. In PRC, the money of property and land developers flown from bank loans will be used for buying rights of land use assets from the regime which rejects privatisation of land and sells rights of land use assets deprived from former occupants using force (i.e., forced demolition) funded with aforementioned tax fund, prepaid money for rights of land use that arose from bank loans of customers, bank loans of the developer itself or its shareholders or equity fund. The land of China CCP claimed initially in 1949 belongs to the people but the land's deposition rights have never been granted to the people and land deposition rights have never been granted to the people, but CCP entities could occupy the land for free, such as land allocated and delivered to administration agencies. To develop land into real estate yielding many taxes, the loans fund is used to:

Occupy arable land with force resulting in food crisis and homeless peasants;

Destroy forest resulting in flood, less carbon dioxide absorption and less production of oxygen, contributing to global warming and "natural" disasters;

Buy steel made from coal and iron ores, many of which are imported from Australia and that give leverage of coercing Australia to CCP for revenging Australian requirement of investigation of coronavirus origin while some are produced in Xinjiang and Mongolia where both genocide and environment destruction have been going on and carbon emission arises from coal burning and mining;

...

What makes matters worse is that the loans to developers may result in properties unwanted by customers or even uncompleted projects finally that cause resources wastage.

Mortgage loans entitling CCP regimes to future tax revenue immediately.

Because loans to customers including taxes are revenues of real estate developers taxed when there's a transfer of control over the property and principals have to be paid back in the forthcoming decades of years, the customers bear the future decades of years' taxes for the time being that must be repaid in future. As far as the property developers are concerned, the taxes are prepaid when customers prepaid consideration for the properties. So, in the notes to financial statements of PRC developers, there are many prepaid taxes included in the "Prepayments", "Other current assets" or "Other assets" account. One example is what was shown on page 233 of 2019 Annual Report of Vanke. On page 78 of 2019 Annual Report of Vanke, it was shown that HSBC took part in Vanke's investor meetings in 2019 as investors that may be related to borrowings in USDs for about thirty billion RMB by Vanke Real Estate Hong Kong via a MTN Programme listed on the Stock Exchange of Hong Kong with interest-bearing at 2.95% to 5.35% per annum shown on page 244 and page 262 of 2019 Annual Report of Vanke.

The regimes pay out that fund arising from such future revenue in the current fiscal year and then it's no surprise that both HK police and PRC police are powerful and energetic to install surveillance system supported with the most advanced AI technology, support Alibaba and WeChat to collect privacy information, conduct BGY campaign to silence western government officials over HK crisis problem and Huawei security concern and suppress HK dissidents.

HSBC not only made CCP regimes capable of collecting future taxes via mortgage loans, but also bought bonds issued by CCP regimes which in fact granted CCP regimes to future taxes as the bonds had to be repaid with future taxpayers' money. On page 140 of HSBC annual report, it was told that there were 71.1 billion US dollars PRC assets outstanding, including 14.0 billion US dollars PRC Government and official institutions assets.

Property prices including taxes collected ahead of decades of years inflated by HSBC loans will leave few cash available for businesses to pay dividend, wages and salaries and makes businesses hard to survive both in HK and PRC. Therefore, household debt to disposable income both in HK and PRC increased yearly.

Household Debt and Leverage

(Percent)

Sources: BIS, and IMF staff calculations.

(Picture source: 2019 HK disposable income¹⁸)

Household Debt Levels as a Proportion of GDP and Income, China and United States, 2005 - 2019

Percent

Source: US Federal Reserve, People's Bank of China, National Bureau of Statistics.

(Picture source: 2005-2019 PRC disposable income¹⁹)

A YouTube video made by The Economist told us that in history not necessarily each citizen had to have the ownership of real estate but banks' lending, encouraged by propaganda and interest

expense deduction in calculating income tax, gave rise to property bubbles. Given limited land supply and property development in HK, property bubbles will only help raise rental price.

(Video source: <https://youtu.be/kkVEt5tC2xU>)

Such loans made youngsters, with overwhelmed loans, both in HK and PRC lose creativity and animation.

After so many taxes irrelevant to economic value creation but relevant to destruction of economy are included in the loan principals directly or indirectly, how can you count on full recourse of the loan principals and interest? The ECL allowance rate of 1.38% is obviously insufficient to reflect actual bad debt rate.

Suspected financial fraud on customer deposits

HSBC's consolidated balance sheet showed that it had deposit under customer accounts for 1,642.780 billion US dollars. After HSBC received deposits from customers, it froze the customer accounts of HK activists, who were acting for rule of law, democracy and freedom in HK, in the name of observing HK National Security Law that in essence illegally put customers' assets on own hold and disregarded holy right of citizens over private properties. There were several examples showing HSBC no longer honoured holy right of citizens over private properties.

Suspected financial fraud cases committed by HSBC reported by Media

No.	Name of victims	Media report	Date of report
1	Ted Hui Chi-fung, his wife and parents.	Exiled Hong Kong legislator calls for action after HSBC bank accounts frozen ²⁰	7 Dec 2020
2	Cheung Kim-hung	Hong Kong media exec says HSBC accounts frozen after arrest ²¹	27 Aug 2020

3	Pastor Roy Chan, his wife and the Good Neighbor North District Church	A Hong Kong pastor tried to protect democracy activists. Now his bank account is frozen ²²	16 Dec 2020
4	Jimmy Lai	Exclusive: Hong Kong police obtain financial records of arrested democracy activists ²³	26 Jan 2021

The HK National Security Law has never been agreed through representation of Chinese people and the HK police was not acting on the laws agreed on by the HKers commonly. CCP couldn't represent Chinese people. HSBC disregarded such fact and even froze accounts of relatives of pro-democracy activists in HK. On this ground, HSBC has been suspectedly committing financial fraud continually.

Stakeholder Actions in Great Need

Considering the cases above as well as conflict of interest of HSBC due to its investments in debts issued by PRC governments, in addition to HK National Security Law enforcement system over border by CCP through mutual extradition arrangements, other customers and potential customers of HSBC must think twice before placing any deposit. Besides, the current and potential debtholders of HSBC debts, including those presented as “Trading liabilities”, “Debt securities in issue”, “Subordinated liabilities”, etc also should conduct more stringent financial fraud risk analysis and strategy analysis before deciding to continue or withdraw from the business relationship with HSBC.

So should the auditor of HSBC, especially considering the HK PWC's audit working papers unavailable to be inspected by US PCAOB that may be considered as unfollowing the ethical code of “integrity” and “professional behaviour” or refusing “the responsibility to act in the public interest”.

All the stakeholders of HSBC should take actions to take down CCP and terminate HSBC's role in CCP totalitarian expansion to realise sustainable development of human society which is the core of ESG standards.

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